

To Evaluate Peripheral Smears with Hypersegmented Neutrophils-an Etiological Analysis in Tertiary Care Center of North Bihar

Ranjan Kumar Rajan¹, MD Shakir Ahmad², Chittaranjan Dutta³

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Darbhanga Medical College, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, Bihar, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Darbhanga Medical College, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, Bihar, India

³Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Darbhanga Medical College, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, Bihar, India

Received: 10-03-2022 / Revised: 25-04-2022 / Accepted: 05-05-2022

Corresponding author: Dr. MD Shakir Ahmad

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: To evaluate peripheral smears with hypersegmented neutrophils and classify the etiological factors.

Material & Method: This is a prospective study carried out over a period of one year conducted in Department of Pathology, Darbhanga Medical College, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, Bihar, India. EDTA blood samples received in our hematology laboratory were analyzed for hypersegmentation of neutrophils using leishman stained peripheral smears.

Results: Although major cases were contributed by macrocytic anemia, 43.7% cases were having microcytic hypochromic anemia. Out of the 42 cases with normocytic normochromic blood picture; only 12 had subnormal levels of either Vit B12 or folic acid values. Rest of the 30 cases had normal Vit B12 and folic acid levels.

Conclusion: Microcytic hypochromic anemia, myelodysplastic syndromes and inflammatory conditions also can cause hypersegmented neutrophils in peripheral smears. Study also points to increased incidence thrombocytosis in pure Microcytic hypochromic anemia cases compared to other etiological factors which is still to be established with further detailed studies.

Keywords: Hypersegmented neutrophils, Peripheral smear

This is an Open Access article that uses a fund-ing model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Hypersegmented neutrophils are classically seen with folate (vitamin B9) or cobalamin (vitamin B12) deficiency. These morphologic changes of the neutrophil nucleus occur due to impaired DNA synthesis from inadequate substrate or impaired replication from a toxin or

medication effect. Arrest of nuclear maturation, impaired cell division, and unbalanced cell growth results in characteristic large cells with immature nuclei with relative cytoplasmic maturity. Red blood cell macrocytosis often accompanies hypersegmented neutrophils

and can be seen in hypothyroidism, alcohol abuse, uremia, and myelodysplastic syndromes. [1]

Hyper segmentation of neutrophils is defined as presence of 5% or more neutrophils with five or more nuclear lobes or single neutrophil with 6 lobed nucleus. [2] It is usually associated with deficiency of or failure to utilize cobalamin or folate and impaired DNA synthesis is the accepted mechanism for the morphological changes seen in megaloblastosis. [3-4]

Pancytopenia is characterized by low levels of hemoglobin (Hb), Low ANC (Absolute neutrophil count) and low platelets. The list of differentials which can account for this abnormality is extensive, as are the potential investigations and associated treatments. [5]

The co-morbidities result from a variable degree of cytopenia and clonal instability with a tendency to progression mainly into acute myeloid leukemia (AML). [6] Uremia, hyperthermia, drugs including chemotherapy, steroids, G-CSF are also known to produce neutrophil hyper segmentation. [7]

Thus, this study aims to evaluate peripheral smears with hypersegmented neutrophils and classify the etiological factors.

Material & Method:

This is a prospective study carried out over a period of one year conducted in Department of Pathology, Darbhanga Medical College, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, Bihar, India.

A total of 160 Patients classified according to the peripheral smear picture. Patients with microcytic hypochromic anemia were separately assessed for serum Vit B12 and folic acid values using ion capture assay and micro particle enzyme intrinsic factor assay. Presence of thrombocytosis in pure microcytic hypochromic anemia cases were checked separately and it was

compared with presence of thrombocytosis in cases with normal hemogram without microcytic hypochromic anemia.

Patients with known medical conditions like pregnancy, uremia, renal failure and exposure to drugs like chemotherapeutic agents, steroid and G-CSF were excluded.

Methodology

EDTA blood samples received in our hematology laboratory were analyzed for hyper segmentation of neutrophils using leishman stained peripheral smears. Neutrophils hyper segmentation is defined as the presence of five or more five-lobed neutrophils per 100, or any neutrophils with six or more lobes. 160 such cases which satisfied the inclusion criteria were taken as sample size. Complete blood count of individual cases was obtained using ERBA Mannheim H360 analyzer and peripheral smear picture was compared with blood counts.

Results:

Detailed analysis of all cases showed the following details. Age and gender distribution of cases are shown in Table 1. Majority of cases were males and majority of cases were in the age group 40-60.

Cases were further analyzed for associated peripheral smear picture. Although major cases were contributed by macrocytic anemia, 36.25% cases were having microcytic hypochromic anemia. Detailed picture is given in Table 2.

Table 3 clearly shows that out of the 25 cases with normocytic normochromic blood picture, only 10 had subnormal levels of either Vit B12 or folic acid values. Rest of the 15 cases had normal Vit B12 and folic acid levels. Out of the 160 cases with hyper segmented neutrophils in peripheral smear 36% cases were having pure microcytic hypochromic anemia without any vit B12 or folic acid deficiency.

Platelet count of all cases was assessed. Results are shown in Table 4. 1.5-4.5

lakh/microliter is considered as normal platelet count. Out of the 160 cases, only 19 had Platelet count less than

1.5lakh/cmm. 141 cases had platelet count in the normal range.

Table 1: Age and gender distribution of all cases showing hyper segmented neutrophils in peripheral smears

Gender	Below 20	20-40	40-60	Above 60	Total
Male	8	18	44	27	97
Female	6	10	33	14	63
Total	14	28	77	41	160

Table 2: Peripheral smear picture of cases with hypersegmented neutrophils

Macrocytic anemia	70
Microcytic hypochromic anemia	58
Normocytic normochromic blood picture	25
Myelodysplastic syndrome	7
Total	160

Table 3: Serum Vit B12 and folic acid values of cases with neutrophil hyper segmentation in microcytic hypochromic blood picture

Vit B12(in pg /ml)	Observed frequency	Folic acid (in ng/ml)	Observed frequency
<200pg/ml	9	<2ng/ml	5
200-500pg/ml	28	2-8ng/ml	8
500-700pg/ml	13	8-15ng/ml	30
700-900pg/ml	5	15-20ng/ml	14
>900pg/ml	3	>20ng/ml	1
Total	58		58

Table 4: Correlation of neutrophil hyper segmentation and platelet count

Platelet count	Macrocytic anemia	Microcytic hypochromic Picture (Normal B12 and folic acid)	Microcytic hypochromic Blood picture (subnormalB12 and folic acid)	Myelodysplasia	Normocytic Normochromic Blood Picture
<1.5 lakh/microlitre	11	1	2	2	3
1.5-4.5 lakh/microlitre	54	19	12	5	13
>4.5lakh/microlitre	5	21	3	0	9
Total	70	41	17	7	25

Discussion:

Hypersegmented neutrophils without red blood cell macrocytosis, as in our patient, has been described in patients with hyperthermia, uremia, and concurrent megaloblastic and microcytic anemia from combined folate and/ or cobalamin

deficiency along with iron deficiency or thalassemia. As the finding of hypersegmented neutrophils precedes macrocytosis, neutrophil hyper segmentation without macrocytosis may represent early cobalamin and folate deficiency. [8]

The term “botryoid” refers to nuclei that appear like a cluster of grapes around a stem.[9]. Botryoid nuclei have been described in patients with hyperthermia due to cocaine and methamphetamine use, [10] malignant hyperthermia, neuroleptic malignant syndrome, [11] and autoimmune disorders such as rheumatoid arthritis, psoriatic arthritis, and systemic sclerosis. [12] In comparison, the multilobed nuclei in cobalamin and folate deficiency appear disorganized.

The importance of B12 as a cofactor in the body for varying reactions has been well studied. It plays an essential role in DNA synthesis, hematopoiesis and myelination. Given the hematological picture presented in both cases, the list of differentials was extensive. However, the characteristic finding of oval macrocytosis and hypersegmented neutrophils was key in both cases, ultimately resulting in the diagnosis of B12 deficiency. [13] A normal neutrophil has up to three to four lobes in its nucleus, and a hypersegmented neutrophil has five or greater. Microscopic criteria cite 1 neutrophils with six lobes or 5% with five lobes as a relevant finding. There were several other abnormalities in the blood profile, namely the elevated LDH and elevated bilirubin. The latter findings create a picture which is similar to a hemolytic anemia; however, in this case, the etiology is lysis of immature cells due to ineffective erythropoiesis and associated release of LDH. [14-15]

There are some explanations in previous studies that neutrophil changes in iron deficiency represent a recent event with only young red cells and not the overall population of red cells, showing a reduced folate content. [16-17] Some other studies shows that iron deficiency can affect the folate dependent degradation of FIGLU catalyzed by enzyme FIGLU transferase. [18-19] It is also possible that iron deficiency may directly influence DNA synthesis. [20-21]

Vitamin B12 deficiency is prevalent among the older population. The Framingham study demonstrated a prevalence of 12% among older people living in the community while some estimates suggest as many as 30%–40% in institutions, with the predominant pathology food-cobalamin malabsorption and pernicious anemia. [22] The presentation is usually insidious due to the gradual reduction in the stores of B12 rather than an acute decline. Symptoms are polymorphic and include hematological, neuropsychiatric, digestive including altered bowel habit and possibly gynecological. [22]

Neutrophil hyper segmentation and thrombocytosis can be expected as a part of megaloblastic anemia. But it may be also seen in iron deficiency anemia also. [23-25]

Conclusion:

Causes of neutrophil hyper segmentation, microcytic hypochromic anemia, myelodysplastic syndromes and inflammatory conditions also can cause hypersegmented neutrophils in peripheral smears. Study also points to increased incidence thrombocytosis in pure microcytic hypochromic anemia cases compared to other etiological factors which is still to be established with further detailed studies.

References:

1. Herbert V. Nutrition science as a continually unfolding story: the folate and vitamin B12 paradigm. *Am J Clin Nut.* 1987;46(3):387–402.
2. Agarwal KN. Indicators for assessment of anemia and iron deficiency in community. *Pediatr Oncall J.* 2010;7 (2):29–34.
3. Westerman DDA, Evans D, Metz J. Neutrophil hyper segmentation in iron deficiency anemia: A case control study. *Br J Haematol.* 1999;107(3):5 12–5.

4. Daniel D. Im, MD, Cynthia H. Ho, MD, wz and Randall Y. Chan. Hypersegmented Neutrophils in an Adolescent Male with Heatstroke. *Pediatr Hematol Oncol* _ Volume 37, Number 6, August 2015.
5. Weinzierl EP, Arber DA. The differential diagnosis and bone marrow evaluation of new-onset pancytopenia. *Am J Clin Pathol* 2013; 139:9–29.
6. Steensma DP. Myelodysplastic syndromes: diagnosis and treatment. *Mayo Clin Proc.* 2015;90(7):969–83.
7. Im DD, Ho CH, Chan RY. Hypersegmented Neutrophils in an Adolescent Male with Heatstroke. *J Pediatr Hematol Oncol.* 2015; 37(6): 488.
8. Hattersley PG, Engels JL. Neutrophilic hyper segmentation without macrocytic anemia. *West J Med.* 1974; 121:179–184.
9. Hernandez JA, Aldred SW, Bruce JR, et al. “Botryoid” nuclei in neutrophils of patients with heatstroke. *Lancet.* 1980; 2:642–643.
10. Chew E, Juneja S. Images in clinical medicine. Botryoid whitecel nuclei. *N Engl J Med.* 2013;368: e22.
11. Ward PCJ, McKenna RW, Kroft SH. White blood cell changes in hyperthermia. *Br J Haematol.* 2007;13 8:130.
12. Core P, Muti S, Cervini C. Radial segmentation of leukocyte nuclei in some rheumatic disorders. *Rheumatol Int.* 1994; 13:247–249.
13. Stabler SP. Vitamin B12 deficiency. *New England Journal of Medicine* 2013; 368:149–60.
14. Dalsania CJ, Khemka V, Shum M, et al. A sheep in wolf’s clothing. *Am J Med* 2008; 121:107–9.
15. Wjl MSB. *Clinical laboratory Hematology*, 2010.
16. Omer A, Finlayson ND, Shearman DJC, Samson RR, Girdwood RH. Plasma and erythrocyte folate in iron deficiency and folate deficiency. *Blood.* 1970;35(6):821–8.
17. Roberts PD, John DS, Sinha R, Stewart JS, Baird IM, Coghill NF, et al. Apparent folate deficiency in iron deficiency anemia. *Br J Haematol.* 1971;20(2):165–75.
18. Chanarin I, Bennett MC, Berry V. Urinary excretion of histidine derivative in megaloblastic anemia and other conditions in comparison with the folic acid clearance test. *J Clin Pathol.* 1962;15(3):269–73.
19. Vitale JJ, Restrepo A, Riker JB, Hellerstin EE. Secondary folate deficiency induced in rat by dietary iron deficiency. *J Nutr.* 1966;88(3): 315–22.
20. Hershko CH, Karsai A, Eylon L, Izak G. The effect of chronic iron deficiency on some biochemical functions of the human hematopoietic tissue. *Blood.* 1970;36(3):321–9.
21. Pillay J, Kamp VM, Hoffen EV, Visser T, Tak T, Lammers J. A subset of neutrophils in human systemic inflammation inhibits T cell responses through Mac-1. *J Clin Invest.* 2012;1 22:327–36.
22. A ndrès E, Loukili NH, Noel E, et al. Vitamin B12 (cobalamin) deficiency in elderly patients. *CMAJ* 2004; 171:251–9.
23. Duzgun S, Yildirmak Y, Cetinkaya F. Neutrophil hyper segmentation and thrombocytosis in children with iron deficiency anemia. *Turk J Pediatr.* 2005; 47:251–4.
24. Mahmood T, Robinson WA, Hamstra RD, Wallner SF. Macrocytic anemia, thrombocytosis and non-lobulated megakaryocytes: the 5qsyndrome, a distinct entity. *Am J Med.* 1979;66 (6):946–50.
25. Tomasi, D., & Webb, S. Human Gastrointestinal Microbiota and Neural Activity: Effects of Probiotics on Mental and GI Health. *Journal of Medical Research and Health Sciences*, 2020;3(9), 1070–1077.